

Effect of Tax Knowledge on the Alternative Dispute Resolution among Three Star Hotels in Mombasa County, Kenya

Author's Details:

Jefwa Wangu William¹ Eric Mathuva² Christopher Njoroge³

¹School of Business and Economics, Kenya Methodist University (KeMU), Kenya

²Senior Lecturer, Kenya Methodist University (KeMU), Kenya

³Senior Lecturer, Kenya Methodist University, (KeMU), Kenya

Abstract

any good tax system requires tax dispute resolution (ADR) mechanisms. A dispute can occur where the tax authority and the tax payers have varied in views on tax payer liability. Alternative dispute resolution is a voluntary, interactive and mediated dialogue between a taxpayer and the Commissioner about a tax dispute. Globally it is recommended that at least 80% of tax disputes should be resolved through Alternative Dispute Resolution. Kenya introduced the Alternative Dispute Resolution framework in July 2015. The purpose of this study was to establish the effect of tax knowledge on the Alternative Dispute Resolution, among three star Hotels in Mombasa County, Kenya. The specific objective of this study was to establish effects of fiscal tax knowledge on the alternative dispute resolution among three star Hotels in Mombasa County. The theories that anchored this study included; conflict resolution theory, ability-to-pay tax theory, cost of services theory and the benefit theory of taxation. A descriptive survey study design was used. Data was therefore obtained from a sample made of forty six (46). The study made use of questionnaires for data collection. The researcher sought a letter of introduction from the university authority, which he used to seek a research permit from the National Council for Science, Technology and Innovation. The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25 was used in analyzing the data. Further, the Regression analysis was used to examine the effect of tax knowledge on the Alternative Dispute Resolution among three star hotels in Mombasa County, Kenya. The study concluded fiscal tax knowledge studied had significant effect on the alternative dispute resolution among three star Hotels in Mombasa County, Kenya as indicated by the strong coefficient of correlation and a p-value which is less than 0.05. The overall effect of the analyzed factors was very high as indicated by the coefficient of determination. The study found out that Fiscal tax knowledge has significant impact on tax dispute resolution. It is therefore recommended that hotel owners, KRA from ADR section and tax consultants device ways to be more visible, intervene and participate at all times in cases relating to tax disputes. This study focused on the effect of tax knowledge on the Alternative Dispute Resolution among three star Hotels in Mombasa County, Kenya. This study recommended that a further study be carried out on other factors such as hospitality culture; technology complexity among others that might have effect on the Alternative Dispute Resolution among three star Hotels in Mombasa County, Kenya.

Keywords: Tax Knowledge, Hotel Industry, Dispute Resolution

1. Introduction

Alternative dispute resolution (ADR) tools for tax disputes are necessary for any effective tax system. When the tax authorities and the taxpayers hold opposing opinions regarding the tax payer's responsibility, a disagreement may result. The discrepancies frequently result from both parties believing that the other party did not correctly apply the law. The Kenya Revenue Authority (KRA) has turned to alternative dispute resolution (ADR) techniques as a result of the unfavorable effects of resolving a tax issue through a court process. Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR) is a voluntary, interactive, and moderated discussion regarding a tax issue between a taxpayer and the Commissioner (KRA). Applying ADR techniques to settle tax disputes has benefits like lower costs, quicker resolution, and improved relationships between the parties.

2.0 Research gap

The hospitality industry's share of the global Gross Domestic Product (GDP) in 2018 was 10.4%. As a result, it is essential to monitor because it contributes to tax revenue, which finances a nation's economy (Bierling, 2019). Goals for revenue collection are a challenge for the Kenya Revenue Authority (KRA). The KRA collection increased in the 2017–2018 fiscal year by Ksh. 1.17 trillion, falling short of the intended Kshs. 1.4 trillion. KRA raised Kshs in the 2018–2019 budget years. 1.58 trillion, making the overall amount raised Kshs. 1.605 trillion. KRA also offers Kshs. A Kshs is worth 1.607 trillion. 1.8 trillion target (KRA, 2020). This is a strong sign that there is a problem with revenue collection. The KRA is in charge of collecting taxes by administering and enforcing tax legislation.

Previous studies have focused on ADR mechanisms and revenue collection. Research on alternative dispute resolution techniques was done by Kashindi (2017), who found that while the process has been helpful in settling existing tax disputes in the nation, it hasn't yet been generally adopted there. Mohammed and Muturi (2018) looked into the variables that affect how well Kenyan county governments collect taxes. The results show that improving compliance is necessary to boost the effectiveness of revenue collection. A report on Kenya's rules governing alternative dispute settlement was also released by Muigua (2018).

The number of applicants for ADR was 559 in years 2021/2022 compared to 493 who applied in the year 2020/2021, an increase of 13%. This confirms the growth in the number of tax payers who are increasingly embracing ADR preference to other dispute resolutions mechanism (Business daily, 2022). This demonstrates that the tax knowledge level of tax payers is progressing. The extent of this tax knowledge is the reason for this study and forms the gap knowledge. It is against this backdrop that the study seeks to establish the effect of tax knowledge on the Alternative Dispute Resolution among three star Hotels in Mombasa County, Kenya.

The three star hotels are the ideal research subjects because they are unstable businesses that require special care. Every little tool at their disposal can make a huge difference when taking into account their nature. Due to this, a lot of Kenyan three-star hotels decide to remain in the unofficial sector because they believe the cost of compliance is too high, and the majority of those that pay only do so under pressure from the government (Baru, 2019).

2.1 : General Objective of the study

The general purpose of this study was to establish the effect of tax knowledge on the Alternative Dispute Resolution among three star Hotels in Mombasa County, Kenya.

2.1.1 Specific objectives

(a) To establish the effect of fiscal tax knowledge on the alternative dispute resolution among three star Hotels in Mombasa County, Kenya

2.2: Study research question

(a) Does fiscal tax knowledge have effect on the alternative dispute resolution among threestar Hotels in Mombasa County, Kenya?

2.3: Conflict Resolution Theory

Burton first presented the conflict resolution idea in 1962. Key proponents of the theory include Kelman (1993),

Schellenberg (1996), and Hansen (2008). The study is informed on the applicability of this theory since it makes the premise that working well with others to solve problems is the best method to overcome conflict.

Additionally, it compares resolving disputes to a game of winners and losers in which conflicting parties compete. The norms that apply to cooperative behavior include respect, responsibility, honesty, empowerment, and loving behavior toward friends or other group members (Deutsch, 2011).

Oladipupo and Obazee (2020) used a survey research approach to examine the effects of tax payer information and penalties on tax compliance among small and medium-sized businesses in Nigeria. The Ordinary Least Square regression approach was used to examine the data from the survey. The findings demonstrated that tax compliance was positively and significantly impacted by general tax knowledge. The study demonstrates that tax knowledge has a greater propensity to encourage tax compliance. This study aims to determine how tax knowledge affects alternative dispute settlement.

2.4: Conceptual framework

This framework depicts the progression of the link between the dependent variable and the independent variable (tax knowledge) (Alternative dispute resolution). The conceptual framework in figure 2.1 represents the variables and the associated parameters under examination.

Figure 2.1: Conceptual Framework

3. Methodology

This study employed a descriptive survey design. The decision to utilize a descriptive research survey approach was made since it allows for the description of characteristics as well as the testing of the association between variables. The population or universe under study in this instance consisted of all three-star hotels, KRA employees working in ADR's tax resolution section, and tax consultants. The researcher examined all (8) three star hotels in Mombasa County since it is practicable to sample all three star hotels in Kenya that are involved in tax issues with the Kenya Revenue Authority. To include all 16 respondent hotels—2 members, made up of the owner and accountant, 15 members of the KRA's tax resolution division staff, and 15 tax consultants working in Mombasa County—a census sample technique was used. Questionnaires were employed by the researcher to gather data for this investigation. The researcher used the "drop-and-pick later" method to distribute the questionnaires, which involved dropping them off to the respondents and picking them up a week later. Data analysis was done using the SPSS version 25 statistical package for social sciences. Data interpretation uses descriptive analysis metrics including frequency, percentage, means, and standard deviation. In Mombasa County, Kenya, three star hotels were studied using regression analysis to see how tax knowledge affected ADR.

4. Study Results

4.1 Response rate

This represented a response rate of 85%, which was higher than the recommended response rate of 60% by Mugenda and Mugenda (2012) for the descriptive studies reported in each part and is thought to be high enough to justify generalization of findings as shown in figure 4.1.

Figure 4.1: Response Rate of the Respondents

Table 1 Response Rate

4.2: Reliability Test

In order to ascertain a questionnaire's internal validity, a researcher conducted a pilot test on 10% (5 respondents) of the target (46) in Kwale County. The findings were as summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Reliability Analysis

Statements	Cronbach's Alpha	Number of Items
Fiscal tax knowledge	0.812	4

Cronbach's Coefficient Alpha in the table 1 reveals that fiscal had reliability of a value ($\alpha=0.802$). This demonstrates the scales were reliable as their reliability values exceeded the prescribed threshold of 0.70, which is considered acceptable.

4.3: Descriptive results

4.3.1 Fiscal tax knowledge

The study's first objective was to determine how fiscal tax knowledge affected alternative dispute resolution in Mombasa County, Kenya's three-star hotels. Respondents were asked to answer a series of questions and provide their comments regarding the impact of fiscal tax knowledge on the alternative dispute resolution process among three star hotels in Mombasa County, Kenya. The likert scale was further rearranged so that 1-2 represented disagree, 2.1-3 represented undecided, and 3.1-5 represented agree in order to aid in the analysis of these objective results. The findings in Table 2 demonstrate that knowledge of fiscal taxes has an impact on the use of ADR among three-star hotels in Mombasa County, Kenya. This was shown by the majority of respondents (33, or 85%) who agreed that understanding fiscal taxes has a big impact on resolving tax disputes. Thus, taxpayers' fiscal tax awareness is a driving force behind the recent surge in the usage of ADR, and hotel management, together with other stakeholders, should support training in taxpayers' fiscal tax knowledge.

The respondents agreed and stated that fiscal tax knowledge has considerable impact on tax dispute resolution as demonstrated with a mean of 4.6154 and standard deviation of .59007. The analysis of various aspects of fiscal tax knowledge was furthered and is displayed in table 2. The respondents agreed that hotel owners should work to improve their understanding of fiscal taxes, as evidenced by the respondents' mean of 4.2308 and standard deviation of .77668. With a mean of 4.2821 and a standard deviation of .79302, respondents also concurred that tax knowledge benefits both the government and tax payers. With a mean of 4.2051 and a standard deviation of .76707, the respondents further confirmed that educated taxpayers are aware of alternative dispute resolution options. These results are consistent with those of Oladipupo and Obazee (2020), who used a survey research approach to examine the influence of tax payers' knowledge and penalties on tax compliance among small and medium-sized firms in Nigeria. The Ordinary Least Square regression approach was used to examine the data from the survey. The findings demonstrated that tax compliance was positively and significantly impacted by general tax knowledge. The study demonstrates that tax knowledge has a greater propensity to encourage tax compliance.

Table 2: Fiscal tax knowledge

Statements	N	Disagree	Unsure	Agree	Mean	Std Dev.
Fiscal tax knowledge has significant impact on tax dispute resolution	39	2(5%)	4(10%)	33(85%)	4.6154	.59007
Hotel owners should seek to advance their fiscal tax knowledge and awareness	39	3(8%)	9(23%)	27(69%)	4.2308	.77668
Fiscal tax knowledge benefits both government and tax payers	39	1(3%)	6(15%)	32(82%)	4.2821	.79302
Educated taxpayers are aware of alternative dispute resolution opportunities	39	3(8%)	11(28%)	25(64%)	4.2051	.76707

4.3.2 Alternative dispute resolution

The main goal of this study was to determine how tax knowledge affected alternative dispute resolution. As shown in table 3, the majority of respondents [35 (89 percent)] agreed that ADR has helped to reduce the backlog of tax objections, demonstrating that using ADR can speed up the resolution of objection cases. Furthermore, according to the respondents, ADR has significantly lowered the backlog of tax objections. A mean score of 4.4103 and a standard deviation of .84970 illustrate this. Additionally, the respondents noted that the number of tax disputes has significantly decreased as a result of ADR initiatives to a greater extent, as demonstrated by a mean of 4.3590 and a standard deviation of 1.01274. Regarding voluntary disclosure, it was stated that Mombasa County hotels had been heavily urged to participate by ADR. This response is demonstrated by a mean score of 4.3333 and a standard deviation of 1.08418, which indicates that the owner of the hotel freely provides information about their tax situation. The respondents were in agreement on the topic of whether the ADR project has enhanced government income in Mombasa County, as shown by a mean of 4.4459 and a standard deviation of .94018. Furthermore, as shown by a mean of 4.4872 and a standard deviation of .94233, the respondents were in agreement that ADR has experienced an increase in effective and amicable settlement of conflicts. Last of all respondents stated that ADR has increasingly gained acceptance, traction and public confidence to a large extent. This is depicted by a mean value of 4.4128 and standard deviation of 0.95230 as indicated in Table 3.

Data from KRA, which said that "KRA has recovered over Sh6.6 billion in taxes revenues from disputes settled under the Alternative Dispute Resolution process in less than two years," is evidence for this conclusion. Before the ADR framework was introduced on June 17, 2015, there were numerous tax issues involving more than Ksh.35 billion locked up. ADR has been used to settle about 140 tax issues that were pending before the Tax Tribunal.

Table 3: Alternative dispute resolution

Statements	N	Disagree	Unsure	Agree	Mean	Std Dev.
ADR has reduced the backlog of tax objections	39	3(8%)	1(3%)	35(89%)	4.4103	.84970
The number of tax disputes have gone down drastically due to ADR initiatives	39	2(5%)	3(8%)	34(87%)	4.3590	1.01274
ADR has encourage voluntary disclosure by hotels in Mombasa County	39	4(10%)	5(13%)	30(77%)	4.3333	1.08418
ADR initiative has increased government revenues in Mombasa County	39	4(10%)	3(8%)	32(82%)	4.4459	.94018
ADR has seen an increase in efficient and amicable settlement of disputes	39	1(3%)	10(26%)	31(71%)	4.4872	.94233
ADR has increasingly gained acceptance, traction and public confidence	39	3(8%)	2(5%)	34(87%)	4.5128	.95230

4.4 Inferential results

4.4.1 Correlations Analysis

The goal of the study was to perform a correlation analysis. Both the coefficient of correlation and the coefficient of determination were relevant here. This was done in an effort to establish the link between the independent and dependent variables. Table 4 from the study's data demonstrates the relationship between the study variables and results using Karl Pearson's coefficient of correlation (r). The results showed a clear positive association between the dependent variable and the independent factors (fiscal tax knowledge) and dependent variable (alternative dispute resolution). From the analysis, the findings indicate that the coefficient of correlation " r " equal to 0.789 ($P < 0.05$) for fiscal tax knowledge. This shows that there is a strong significant positive relationship between independent variables (fiscal tax knowledge) and dependent variable (ADR).

Table 4: Correlations

Variables		Alternative Dispute Resolution
Alternative Dispute Resolution	Pearson Correlation	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
	N	39
Fiscal Tax Knowledge	Pearson Correlation	.789**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
	N	39

5.0 The study conclusions

As shown by the strong coefficient of correlation and a p-value of less than 0.05, the study came to the conclusion that fiscal tax knowledge analyzed had a substantial impact on the alternative dispute resolution among three star hotels in Mombasa County, Kenya. The coefficient of determination showed that the examined factor had a fairly strong overall impact. The total p-value of 0.000, or less than 0.05 (5%) is a hint that the analyzed variables are relevant and, at the computed 95 percent threshold of significance, significant. This suggests that the independent variable under investigation, namely fiscal tax knowledge has a significant impact on alternative dispute settlement among three-star hotels in Mombasa County, Kenya.

Recommendations

According to the study, understanding fiscal taxes significantly affects how tax disagreements are resolved. Therefore, it is advised that hotel owners, KRA from the ADR division, and tax experts devise means of becoming more visible, intervening, and participating at all times in matters relating to tax disputes.

REFERENCES

- Baru, A. (2019). The impact of tax knowledge on tax compliance. . *Journal of Advanced Research in Business and Management Studies*, 6(2), 22-30.
- Bornman, M., & Ramutumbu, P. (2019). "A conceptual framework of tax knowledge",. *Meditari Accountancy Research*, Vol. 27 No. 6, pp. 823-839. <https://doi.org/10.1108/MEDAR-09-2018-0379>.
- Bierling, L. (2019). Adopting the best dispute resolution method in the Travel and Hospitality industry using Multi-Attribute Decision Making Models, *PM World Journal*, Vol. VIII, Issue III (April).
- Fauziati, P., Minovia, A. F., Muslim, R. Y., & Nasrah, R. (2017). The impact of tax knowledge on tax compliance case study in kota padang, Indonesia. *Journal of Advanced Research in Business and Management Studies*.
- Kanyi, B. G. (2019). Kenya's tax dispute resolution system: A dispute system design evaluation. (Thesis, Strathmore University). Retrieved from <http://suplus.suplus.plus>.
- Kirchheiner, C. (2020). Alternative tax dispute resolutions can revolutionize the Tanzania tax regime. Deloitte Touche Tohmatsu Limited.
- Alm, J., Kirchler, E. & Muehlibacker, S. (2012). Combining psychology and economics in the analysis of compliance: From enforcement to cooperation. *Economic Analysis and Policy*, 42(2), 133-151.
- Alm, J., McClelland G.H. & Schulze, W.D. (2012). Why do people pay taxes? *Journal of Public Economics*, 48(1), 21- 38.
- Antonides, G. & Robben, H.S.J. (2015). True positives and false alarms in the detection of tax evasion. *Journal of Economic Psychology*, 16(4), 617-40.
- Bird, R.M. (2014). Taxation and development: What have we learned from fifty years of research? *Public finance and management*, 13(4), 266-288.
- Bird, R.M. & Wallace, S. (2013). Is it really so hard to tax the hard-to-tax? The Context and Role of Presumptive Taxes; prepared for a Conference on the Hard to Tax Sector. *Andrew Young School of Policy Studies*, 15(16), 45-65.
- Edward, K.S. & Ambrose, J. (2017). Impact of online tax filing on tax compliance among SMEs In Kibuezi in sub country in Kenya. *International Journal of current Research*, 9(1), 45196-45206.
- Engelschalk, M. (2012). Small business taxation in transition countries. *Journal of Economic Psychology*, 29(2), 210-25.
- Helhel, Y. & Ahmed, Y. (2014). Factors affecting tax attitudes and tax compliance: A survey study in Yemen. *European Journal of business and management*, 6(22), 45-65.
- Hite, P.A., Stock, T. & Cloyd, C.B. (2013). Reasons for preparer usage by small business. Hughes, S. (2014). Research and Education.
- Jaidi, J., Noordin, R., Ahmad, N. & Kassim, A.W.M. (2013). Individual taxpayers perception towards selfassessment system: A case of Sabah. *Journal of the Asian Academy of Applied Business*, 2(1), 56-65.
- Karlinsky, S., Burton, H. & Blanthorne, C. (2012). Perception of tax evasion as a crime. *E-Journal of Tax Research*, 2(2), 226-240.
- Lignier, P., Evans, C. & Tran-Nam. B (2014). Tangled up in a tape: The continuing tax compliance plight of the small and medium enterprise business section. *Journal of Economic Psychology*, 29(2), 210-25.
- Listokin, Y. & Schizor, D.M. (2012). I like to pay taxes: Tax payer support for government spending and the efficiency of the system.
- Loo, E.C. (2016). The influence of the introduction on self-assessment on compliance behaviour of individual taxpayers in Malaysia, PhD thesis, University of Sydney, (2011).